

HISTORY OF EARLY MUSEUMS IN CENTRAL ASIA

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the emergence of the first museums, the role of museums in the life of society, the processes of the formation of museums in Central Asia, the organization of museums related to industries and their activities.

Keywords: Central Asia, museum, exhibit, art, culture, cultural relations, history, military memorial museum, manuscript, miniature, museum of Central Asia, health museum.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada dastlabki muzeylarning paydo bo'lishi, muzeylarning jamiyat hayotidagi tutgan o'rni O'rta Osiyodagi muzeylarning shakllanishi jarayonlari, sohalarga oid muzeylarning tashkil etilishi va ularning faoliyati haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: O'rta Osiyo, muzey, eksponat, san'at, madaniyat, madaniy aloqalar, tarix, harbiy memorial muzey, qo'lyozma, miniatyura, O'rta Osiyo muzeyi, sog'liqni saqlash muzeyi.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о появлении первых музеев, роли музеев в жизни общества, процессах становления музеев в Средней Азии, организации музеев, связанных с отраслями и их деятельностью.

Ключевые слова: Средняя Азия, музей, экспонат, искусство, культура, культурные связи, история, военно-мемориальный музей, рукопись, миниатюра, музей Средней Азии, музей здоровья.

Introduction. The activities of museums provide a lot of knowledge about the development of humanity in the process of historical development, its achievements and the rich cultural and spiritual heritage left behind. The ability of aesthetic artistic perception, which arises as a result of studying the activities of museums, arouses in people the desire to reflect the world, its creatures, events, and processes in the environment in various forms.

Main Part. Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and

“Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.443 of April 21 [1].

The very word “Mozi” involuntarily invites the imagination to the border of the distant past, draws the old land full of secrets and times to the beckoning of times. We try to illuminate the dark layers of ancient history with the light of thought and to cover our past, even if only a little. Let’s take a look at how difficult, difficult and extremely good and instructive the paths of history are. After all, where a person's gaze falls, there is a footprint, a remnant of creativity. The beauty, wealth, miraculous nature, art, and rare works of our country are known to the whole world. This country of ours is like a unique and elegant work of art found from the depths of centuries. In the depths of our country, we find structures and buildings made of mainly straw, raw brick, baked brick, ceramics and stones. As physical evidence, there are precious stones, gold, and silver household tools, various decorations, and pottery. Ancient jewelry, coppersmithing, engraving, pottery works, textile king satins, rugs, carpets, all kinds of carved decorations can now be seen only in museums. Showing the artistic, cultural and architectural wealth inherited from several generations of our ancestors and putting them in the eyes of many people has an important educational value.

The peoples of Central Asia have established economic and cultural relations with Middle Eastern and Western countries, such as Urartu, Egypt, Greece, Babylon, and Rome. The famous “Great Silk Road” passed through Central Asia and connected East Asia and India with the countries of the Mediterranean Sea.[2]

Such an attractive country has always been the center of attention of foreign conquerors. For this reason, the historical fate of Central Asia was very difficult: wars of aggression and internal conflicts of the ruling circles often led to riots.

Due to constant massacres, unique palaces, beautiful cities, and unique structures were destroyed, and the collected priceless cultural treasures became the spoils of the victors.

Historian Mukhammad Narshahi testified that the Arabs returned from the battles of Poykand with a large amount of gold, silver, weapons, and valuable clothes. During the period of the Arab occupation, there was no better progress in the collection of treasures and accumulation of cultural wealth.

The establishment of the independent Somani state in Central Asia (IX-X centuries) made a fundamental change in this regard. During this period, in addition to the wealth of the palace, large libraries and archives were built. The

libraries of Bukhara and Shiraz emirates in the 10th century contained all the rare books created by mankind.

Makhmud Ghaznavi, the founder of the Ghaznavid dynasty, also collected a lot of books. Khorezmshah Mukhammad did great things for the development of the country. He built beautiful palaces, castles, and mausoleums. He collected rare material and spiritual wealth, but these unique monuments of art and culture, entire cities were lost due to the invasion of Mongol invaders. Libraries were burned, cultural life retreated 100 years.

After 150 years, Science and culture began to sprout again in Central Asia. In particular, the establishment of a single centralized state by Amir Temur and the making of Samarkand the capital led to the accumulation of great wealth. Architectural monuments, mausoleums, mosques-madrasas, palaces were built. Amir Timur brought to Samarkand ancient manuscripts, correspondence and embassy documents of khans and emirs, the holy book of the Muslim world, "Uthman's Koran" (VII century) from the conquered countries. He founded the world-famous Temur Library. Temur's beloved grandson, Mirzo Ulugbek, the great astronomer of the East, enriched the library even more.

Prince Baisungur Mirza (died 1433), the son of Amir Temur's grandson Shah Rukh, built the palace library in Herat. Oriental scholar According to A. Yakubovsky, thanks to Boysungur's refined taste and deep knowledge, such a large library was created in Herat, in which several groups of calligraphers, elegant picture masters (painters), goldsmiths, cover makers, scientists created. In the library, not only copying and decoration of books, but also philological and textological studies were carried out. In 1442, the complete text of Ferdavsi's "Shahnoma" was copied and written in this library.[3]

Great achievements were made in the fine, applied and architectural arts during the Timurid period. The decoration of palaces, madrasas, mausoleums and other buildings with elegant paintings and patterns has progressed. Bibikhanim Mosque, Gori Amir, Shakhi-zinda, Ahmed Yassavi Mausoleum and Mosque, Aksaroy in Shahrisabz, the observatory and madrasas built by Ulugbek are royal masterpieces of Eastern architecture with their magnificence. skills and intelligence have been demonstrated.

During this period, trade and crafts were so developed that the products made by Bukhara and Samarkand masters were highly valued in the world markets. Herat craftsmen's jewelry, Samarkand, Bukhara dukhoba were very famous. During the period of Timur, the creative works of Movarounnahr masters were viewed.

In 1469, Ali Isfahani's art was praised. The master potter examines the vase. This vase showed the work style of 32 artisans.

Craftsmen demonstrated their skills in newly built mosques, mausoleums and other structures. For example: candlesticks made by craftsmen for the Bibikhanim mosque and the gate of the mosque were the pinnacle of carving art. Tabrez craftsman Abdul-Aziz made a two-ton copper pot for the tomb of Ahmed Yassavi (1381).[4] Candlesticks and chandeliers were made by Izoddin, a craftsman from Isfahan. The interior of Gori Amir after the burial of Timur in 1405 was reminiscent of the "Military Memorial Museum". Each item placed in the mausoleum was a rare historical and cultural monument.

According to the historian Arabshakh, the owner's clothes and weapons were hung on the walls of the mausoleum. These weapons were made of gold and silver and were decorated with precious ruby stones. Under the dome of the mausoleum hung golden and silver chandeliers, reminiscent of the stars in the sky. One candlestick is made of 4000 miskals of gold. silk and dukhoba carpets were laid on the floor in the size of a mausoleum.

Khusayn Boygaro from the Timurid dynasty beautified Herat with beautiful buildings, mosques and madrasahs. Together with Alisher Navoi, the sultan of poetry, he turned Herat into a garden of poets and virtues. During this period, historical scholars Mirkhond (died 1498) and his grandson, historian Khondamir, great painter Kamoliddin Behzod created.

During this period, Herat school of miniature art masters was established, countless manuscripts were copied by talented calligraphers and decorated with gold.

Oriental scholar A. Yu. According to Yakubovsky, Alisher Navoi (1441-1501) had a huge personal library rich in rare manuscripts. Historian Khondamir, artist Behzod and other scholars used this library. Bukhara-Khiva khanates also had a custom to build palaces and private libraries with collections of rare manuscripts and miniatures.

Thus, the first museums in Central Asia appeared in the form of a large display of rare objects, rare manuscripts and other art and craft items.

As a result of the conquest of Central Asia by the Russian invaders and their interest in the natural and cultural resources of this country, the first local history museum was established. This museum is the basis of the current Museum of the History of Uzbekistan and has a history of almost 150 years. Before the October Revolution, the first and only museum in Tashkent was the "Tashkent Museum". After the revolution, museums with wide expositions of

various specialties began to be established. In 1918, an art museum based on his confiscated collection was established in the palace of Prince N. Romanov, the current "Uzbekistan State Art Museum", in 1921, the Old City Museum, in 1925, the revolution under the Institute of Party History of the Central Asian Bureau of the Central Asian Bureau of the Central Asian Committee of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union. Museum and the Old City Museum of Uzbekistan was established in 1926.[5] The Cultural Revolution necessitated the creation of a new museum and the re-equipment of the existing one. In 1930, the Central Asian Museum and Revolution Museum was transformed into the Central Asian History and Revolution Museum. The geology, zoology, botany and anthropology departments of the Central Asian Museum, the agricultural museum and the zoo were transformed into a nature museum. Polytechnic Museum (1933), Museum of Applied Art (1937; permanent exhibition of works of Applied Art in 1937-91) were established on the basis of republican exhibitions. A museum of literature and a museum of struggle against religion were established. In 1940, there were about 5,000 exhibits in the Tashkent Museum. The number of visitors to the museum was about 300,000. The years of the Great Patriotic War were merged into the Central Museum of History, the Museum of Art and the Museum of Literature of the Uzbek SSR, the Museum of History, Culture and Art, and the Polytechnic Museum into the Museum of Nature. A new stage in the construction of museums began in the mid-40s of the 20th century. In 1945, the State Art Museum, located in the old building of the Theater of Russian Young Spectators, was transformed into an independent museum. In 1946, the museum of artistic and scientific propaganda named after Hamza was established, and in 1963 it was turned into a house of scientific atheism in the republic. 1970 V. Lenin Museum, 1972 Museum of Cinematic Art of Uzbekistan, 1973 Museum of Health Care of Uzbekistan, 1975 Museum of the History of Turkestan Military District Troops, 1976 Museum of Friendship of the Peoples of the USSR, 1988 The Museum of Antiques and Jewelry was opened. In the 1960s and 1980s, H. Abdullaev, M. Ashrafiy, S. Borodin, Oybek, G. Ghulam, S. Ainiy, O. Tansikboev, A. Kahhor House Museums, Yu. Fuchik, S. Yesenin Museums, permanent exhibition of Tamarakhonim dresses was founded.[6]

There were 16 large museums in the city of Tashkent in the pre-independence period, which housed about 800,000 exhibits. An average of 1.5 million people visit the museum every year. The museum publishes scientific works, manuals and catalogs. The exhibition of achievements of the national economy of Uzbekistan is included in the list of institutions of the planetarium museum type.

Museums established in Tashkent enterprises, institutions and educational institutions complement the state museum network. In our country, May 18 is marked as the International Day of Museums.

Conclusion. Among the major museums in our capital are the history of the Timurids, the history of Uzbekistan, the memory of the victims of repression, the Museum of Literature and Art, the Museum of Geology, the Museum of Nature, the Museum of Olympic Fame, the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan, Health and a number of other museums. There is. They not only attract people living on the other side of the world with the monuments of our country, but also make them familiar, amuse them and teach them about the history, rich heritage and culture of our country.

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